

Novel topological properties and entropy measurements of zigzag hexagonal cycloarene structure¹

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Abstract

Topological indices are specific chemical descriptors discovered by using graph-theoretical methods, and they are extremely useful in connecting molecules with their physical characteristics. Cycloarenes, a subclass of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, are made by arranging benzene rings in a circular manner. These molecules have received a lot of interest recently due to their unusual electrical characteristics and pore structure, which allow for their rapid practical application. In the current research, topological indices are used to investigate cycloarenes and certain of their oligomers. In this study, we develop analytical formulas of various R, S, Van indices of zigzag hexagonal cycloarene structure. Statistical techniques are also used to analyze the quantitative structure-property relationships of these compounds with different electrical and spectroscopic properties, and the relevance of these indices is then confirmed with supporting data. As an alternative to the conventional idea of thermodynamic entropy, we also give topological index-based Shannon's entropy calculation using the R, S, Van topological concept for the study.

Keywords: Cycloarene, Shannon's entropy, Topological descriptors, Van index, S index, R index

1. Introduction

Chemical graph theory is a concept used in the mathematical chemistry field of topology. It gained popularity as its proponents presented several graph theory applications for mathematical modeling of chemical characteristics [1]. Chemists have established through a substantial body of experimental data that a compound's physicochemical properties are closely related to its molecular structure. Later, additional graph-theoretical techniques were developed to describe diverse chemical compound properties.

The idea of topological indices, which are specific network invariants, is one such key tool. Due to their usage in creating quantitative structure activity (QSAR) and quantitative structure-property relationships

¹ This article is dedicated to all our Palestinian Muslim brothers and sisters who were martyred in the attacks of the cruel terrorist state of Israel. Long live free and prosperous PALESTINE.

(QSPR), which relate a substance's chemical structure to its properties [2, 3], they are becoming more and more important. This research's primary objectives are the introduction of novel entropy measures based on R, S, Van topological indices and the calculation of defined entropies of ZHK(n,p) structure. This makes it easier to calculate different physicochemical parameters of complicated substances that could be challenging to determine through experimental techniques. Because they maximize efficacy and cost, they are frequently utilized in the field of computer-assisted drug development. The mathematical invention and evolution of indices that provide precise links between structures and their function has been the subject of various studies over time [4-6]. A chemical structure known as a benzenoid hydrocarbon system lacks non-hexagonal inner faces due to the fusion of hexagonal carbon rings [7]. Instead, a benzenoid system's outer face is bounded by hexagons after a finite number of hexagonal rings are removed from the interior of the system to create a coronoid hydrocarbon system [8]. Browse [9, 10] and the references therein for more information on coronoid systems and their subclasses. Research on benzenoid and coronoid hydrocarbons started after the discovery of cycloarenes like kekulene, which are produced by linear and angular annulations of benzene units [11]. Due to properties like the magnetocaloric effect brought on by the presence of delocalized electrons, cycloarenes like kekulene and its derivatives have recently attracted the attention of more researchers [12]. Due to the vast range of uses of coronoid structures, theoretical and experimental research on them later grew extensive. Such model molecules for graphite sheets and other carbon-based materials are massive polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) [13]. Their function in transporting metal ions by accommodating them is explained by their electrical properties caused by the superaromaticity and appropriate pore diameters. Most of these PAHs are byproducts of certain chemical reactions involving mineral oil, some of which are particularly hazardous to the environment. This calls for the investigation of their characteristics using both theoretical and experimental techniques [10].

Cycloarenes are recently discovered macrocycles composed of several benzene rings joined together in a linear and angular pattern. The first cycloarene, kekulene, was synthesized in 1978, which led to a lot of inquiries and additional research into the conjugation of macrocycles. Similar cycloarene septulene [14] strengthened a number of facts regarding the electrical and magnetic characteristics of this particular class of PAH. Currently, numerous research are being conducted to understand these compounds' superaromaticity, which explains their increased thermodynamic stability as a result of macrocyclic conjugation [15]. It is clear that research utilizing a variety of topological methodologies assisted in the analysis of a number of electronic features, including the delocalization of pi-electrons. In situations where experimental and quantum chemical methods are challenging to use, graph-theoretical techniques paired with topological investigations of the molecular structure have given researchers tools to assess a variety of broader PAH features [16, 17].

Combinatorics and graph theory-based methods as well as computer-aided simulations are needed to define and evaluate the many physicochemical characteristics of these recently produced compounds. The application of precise and generalized topological quantities is required for the development of robust QSAR and QSPR models. Topological indices provide useful ways to identify and correlate many characteristics in this context by assessing the structural details of complex substances using the concept of molecular graphs. Information-theoretical entropy, which measures how complex a molecule is, has been demonstrated to be strongly correlated with thermodynamic entropy values. As a result, it can be used to identify the phase transition between massive molecular structures. Numerous properties of

molecules, including their chemical spectrum, conjugation, and aromaticity, have been quantified using the topological method and graph theory [16, 18–21]. Numerous benzoid and coronoid hydrocarbons have already been given topological characterisation in the literature [6, 16, 21–24].

Due to their cyclic conjugation and D_{6h} symmetry, cycloarenes like kekulene and their huge oligomers have recently attracted a lot of attention. The mathematical significance of these structures is made obvious by the similarity between their symmetry and the D_6 symmetric group. The computation of degree- and distance-based topological indices has already been finished [6, 21, 25] for straightforward cycloarenes and kekulene oligomers. Our research is driven by the fact that this issue still exists for large D_{6h} symmetric cycloarene compounds with additional benzene rings and related oligomers. Choosing important degree- and degree sum-based indices that may accurately predict the properties of D_{6h} symmetric cycloarenes with various pore diameters and associated oligomers is the major goal of this work. Through the elimination of other indices with weaker chemical application, computational complexity can be decreased.

Here, a number of big polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons with hollow sites and total hexagon ring condensation will be thoroughly explored. The general D_{6h} -symmetric cycloarenes indicated by CY(p), where p is the number of benzene rings on one side of the cycloarene's perimeter, and their oligomers, are given special consideration in the current work. Kekulene oligomers alone make it impossible to study the effects of additional benzene rings added to their periphery without also losing their D_{6h} symmetric cycloarene structure. The current work is the result of a thorough review of the literature [16]. The sole motivation for the parameter p comes from [16] and theoretical curiosity in building massive cavity coronoids. Since cycloarenes serve as the foundation for huge structures with specific pore diameters, they are also known as super-rings. Kekulene and its tessellations' topological index values and information entropy values have already been established [6, 16, 26]. For universal D_{6h} symmetric cycloarenes and their hexagonal and rectangular oligomers, we also give extended relations for computing various topological indices, as well as numerical entropy studies with graphical comparisons. The previous findings are now a specific instance of the new findings made here. In order to demonstrate the significance of the theory, we gathered information on various chemical properties of these compounds created using experimental and quantum chemistry techniques. We then performed correlation analysis to evaluate the accuracy of the indices and how pertinent they are to the surrounding structures. Another creative proposal that deepens the interdisciplinary relationship between graph theory and chemistry is our proposed stability research of various oligomers using information entropy as a viable replacement for classical thermodynamic entropy.

Three alternative framework types of the generalized super-ring CY(p) are taken into account for topological characterization. It is possible to create the zigzag hexagonal cycloarene system by surrounding CY(p) by itself. A zigzag hexagonal structure is anchored in the middle of an armchair hexagonal oligomer, and CY(p) molecules are coupled between each pair of super rings on its six sides in a pyramidal pattern. The structure then takes on a hexagonal shape as more CY(p) molecules are fused in between these pyramidal structures. ZHK(n, p) stands for the zigzag hexagonal structure with n circular CY(p) layers. Fig. 1 show the carbon frameworks of ZHK(n, p) configurations.

Figure 1 ZHK(n,p) cycloarene oligomer growth patterns

2. Computational methods

Throughout the work, we shall refer to the D_{6h} symmetric polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as simple graph G . The edges of the graph G , or $E(G)$, are the C-C bonds, while the vertices of the graph $V(G)$ are the carbon atoms that make up the coronoid system. The expression $e=uv$ designates the edge connecting the vertices u and v . $deg(u)$, the degree of the vertex u in the graph G , stands for the number of other carbon atoms to which a carbon atom u is attached. We will now discuss various graph-theoretical methods employed in our research using this model. $N(v)$ is the set of all neighbouring vertices of v . The sum degree of the vertex v , denoted as S_v , is the total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . The multiplication degree of the vertex v , denoted as M_v , is the multiplication of total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $van(v) = \frac{S_v}{M_v}$ [27]. Also, reverse Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rvan(v) = \frac{M_v}{S_v}$. Van topological indices defined as [27];

The first Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2$.

The second Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$.

The third Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [van(u) + van(v)]$.

The first reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rvan(v)^2$.

The second reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$.

The third reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rvan(u) + rvan(v)]$.

R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $r(v) = M_v + S_v$ [28]. Also, reverse R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rr(v) = \frac{1}{M_v + S_v}$. R topological indices defined as [28]:

The first R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2$.

The second R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$.

The third R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [r(u) + r(v)]$.

The first reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rr(v)^2$.

The second reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$.

The third reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rr(u) + rr(v)]$.

S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $s(v) = |M_v - S_v|$ [29]. Also, reverse S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rs(v) = \frac{1}{|M_v - S_v| + 1}$. R topological indices defined as [29]:

The first S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} s(v)^2$.

The second S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$.

The third S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [s(u) + s(v)]$.

The first reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rs(v)^2$.

The second reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$.

The third reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rs(u) + rs(v)]$.

It is possible for mathematicians to connect graph elements like edges and vertices with probability distributions using the graph entropy measurements, which are divided into intrinsic and extrinsic measures. Chemistry, ecology, sociology, and biology are just a few of the disciplines that frequently use graph entropies [30,31]. Information functional-based graph entropies were developed, evaluated, and presented by Dehmer [32,33]. In addition to analyzing the walk-based graph entropies, Estrada et al. [34] provided a definition of graph entropy that is valid from a physical standpoint. Applications for entropy network measurements include deriving a quantitative definition of a molecular structure and analyzing the biological and chemical characteristics of molecular graphs [35]. Entropy metrics have many applications in the analysis of chemical graphs. They are employed to look at the chemical properties of intricate networks. According to the definition of Shannon's entropy for 2D networks based on the topological index T , defined as;

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Entropy}_T(G) &= \mathbf{Ent}_T(G) \\ &= \log(T(G)) - \frac{1}{T(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

where f is the topological index's structural-functional identifier. In the case of the second Van index, for instance

$f(uv) = van(u)van(v)$ and in the case of the third Van index, for instance $f(uv) = van(u) + van(v)$.

3. Main results

In this section, we first determine the Van, R, and S topological indices for ZHK(n, p) families, followed by the associated entropies of these indices. As shown in Fig. 2, fix a super-ring in the center with a benzene p number on one side and let n to be the dimension of hexagonal oligomers.

ZHK(n,p) families have the following sum, multiplication edge end vertex degree and Van degree partitions which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Edge end vertex sum, multiplication degree and Van degree partition of ZHK(n,p).

Cardinality	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)	$(van(u), van(v))$	$(rvan(u), rvan(v))$
$6n$	(5,5)	(6,6)	(5/6,5/6)	(6/5,6/5)
$12n$	(5,7)	(6,12)	(5/6,7/12)	(6/5,12/7)
$12n(3np - p - 9n + 4)$	(6,7)	(9,12)	(2/3,7/12)	(3/2,12/7)
$12n(3n - 2)$	(6,8)	(9,18)	(2/3,4/9)	(3/2,9/4)
$3n(p - 3)(3n - 1)$	(7,7)	(12,12)	(7/12,7/12)	(12/7,12/7)
$12n$	(7,8)	(12,18)	(7/12,4/9)	(12/7,9/4)
$6n(6n - 5)$	(8,8)	(18,18)	(4/9,4/9)	(9/4,9/4)

ZHK(n,p) families have the following R and S degree partitions which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 S and R edge end vertex degree partition of ZHK(n,p).

Cardinality	$(s(u), s(v))$	$(rs(u), rs(v))$	$(r(u), r(v))$	$(rr(u), rr(v))$
$6n$	(1,1)	(1/2,1/2)	(11,11)	(1/11,1/11)
$12n$	(1,5)	(1/2,1/6)	(11,19)	(1/11,1/19)
$12n(3np - p - 9n + 4)$	(3,5)	(1/4,1/6)	(15,19)	(1/15,1/19)
$12n(3n - 2)$	(3,10)	(1/4,1/11)	(15,26)	(1/15,1/26)
$3n(p - 3)(3n - 1)$	(5,5)	(1/6,1/6)	(19,19)	(1/19,1/19)
$12n$	(5,10)	(1/6,1/11)	(19,26)	(1/19,1/26)

$6n(6n-5)$	$(10,10)$	$(1/11,1/11)$	$(26,26)$	$(1/26,1/26)$
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3.1 Topological indices ZHK(n,p)

The following theorems give the overall Van, R, and S indices representation of ZHK(n,p) .

Theorem 1. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the second Van index of G is;

$$Van^2(G) = \frac{273}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{144}n^2 - \frac{91}{16}np + \frac{9419}{432}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^2(G) &= 6n \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{5}{6} + 12n \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{7}{12} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{7}{12} \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{4}{9} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{7}{12} + 12n \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{4}{9} \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{4}{9} \times \frac{4}{9} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second Van index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 2.

Theorem 2. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the second reverse Van index of G is;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \frac{5832}{49}n^2p - \frac{10449}{196}n^2 - \frac{1944}{49}np - \frac{33183}{9800}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{2r}(G) &= 6n \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{6}{5} + 12n \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{12}{7} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{12}{7} \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{9}{4} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{12}{7} + 12n \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{9}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$+6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{9}{4} \times \frac{9}{4}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second reverse Van index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 3D plot of second Van index of ZHK(n,p)

Figure 3 3D plot of second reverse Van index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 3. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third Van index of G is;

$$Van^3(G(m,n)) = \frac{111}{2} n^2 p - \frac{189}{2} n^2 - \frac{37}{2} np - \frac{113}{2} n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (van(u) + van(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^3(G) &= 6n \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{5}{6}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{7}{12}\right) \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{4}{9}\right) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{4}{9}\right) \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times \left(\frac{4}{9} + \frac{4}{9}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third Van index of Gnetwork is shown in Figure 4.

Theorem 4. Let Gbe a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third reverse Van index of is;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \frac{1026}{7} n^2 p - \frac{999}{7} n^2 - \frac{342}{7} np + \frac{1998}{35} n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{3r}(G) &= 6n \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{6}{5}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{12}{7}\right) \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{9}{4}\right) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{9}{4}\right) \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times \left(\frac{9}{4} + \frac{9}{4}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third reverse Van index of ZHK(n,p) network, , is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4 3D plot of the third Van index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 5. Let be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the second S index of is;

$$S^2(G) = 765n^2p + 2385n^2 - 255np - 2109n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} S^2(G) &= 6n \times 1 \times 1 + 12n \times 1 \times 5 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 3 \times 5 \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times 3 \times 10 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 5 \times 5 + 12n \times 5 \times 10 \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times 10 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second S index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 3D plot of the third reverse Van index of $ZHK(n,p)$

Figure 6 3D plot of the second S index of $ZHK(n,p)$

Theorem 6. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. Then, the second reverse S index of is;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \frac{7}{4}n^2p - \frac{2001}{484}n^2 - \frac{7}{12}np + \frac{2003}{484}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$S^{2r}(G) = 6n \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} + 12n \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{6} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{6}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{11} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6} + 12n \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{11} \\
 &\quad + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second reverse S index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 3D plot of the second reverse S index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 7. Let be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third S index of is;

$$S^3(G) = 378n^2p + 54n^2 - 126np - 174n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (s(u) + s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^3(G) &= 6n \times (1 + 1) + 12n \times (1 + 5) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times (3 + 5) \\
 &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times (3 + 10) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times (5 + 5) + 12n \times (5 + 10) \\
 &\quad + 6n(6n - 5) \times (10 + 10)
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third S index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 3D plot of the third S index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 8. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third reverse S index of is;

$$S^{3r}(G) = 18n^2p - \frac{387}{11}n^2 - 6np + \frac{291}{11}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} S^{3r}(G) &= 6n \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}\right) \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{11}\right) \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{11}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third reverse S index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 3D plot of the third reverse S index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 9. Let be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the second R index of is;

$$R^2(G) = 13509n^2p - 2151n^2 - 4503np - 3549n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} R^2(G) &= 6n \times 11 \times 11 + 12n \times 11 \times 19 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 15 \times 19 \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times 15 \times 26 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 19 \times 19 + 12n \times 19 \times 26 \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times 26 \times 26 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second R index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 20 3D plot of the second R index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 10. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the second reverse R index of is;

$$R^{2r}(G) = \frac{273}{1805} n^2 p - \frac{94008}{305045} n^2 - \frac{91}{1805} np + \frac{16146783}{73820890} n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^{2r}(G(m, n)) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} R^{2r}(G) &= 6n \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{11} + 12n \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{19} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{1}{15} \times \frac{1}{19} \\ &+ 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{1}{15} \times \frac{1}{26} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{19} + 12n \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{26} \\ &+ 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{1}{26} \times \frac{1}{26} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the second reverse R index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 11.

Theorem 11. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third R index of Gis;

$$R^3(G) = 1566n^2 p - 1350n^2 - 522np + 462n$$

Proof. Considering that Gis a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (r(u) + r(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$R^3(G) = 6n \times (11 + 11) + 12n \times (11 + 19) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times (15 + 19) + 12n(3n - 2) \times (15 + 26) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times (19 + 19) + 12n \times (19 + 26) + 6n(6n - 5) \times (26 + 26)$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third R index of ZHK(n,p) network is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11 3D plot of the second reverse R index of ZHK(n,p)

Figure 32 3D plot of the third R index of ZHK(n,p)

Theorem 12. Let be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, the third reverse R index of Gis;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \frac{498}{95} n^2 p - \frac{11328}{1235} n^2 - \frac{166}{95} np + \frac{78106}{13585} n$$

Proof. Considering that is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} R^{3r}(G) = & 6n \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{19}\right) + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \left(\frac{1}{15} + \frac{1}{19}\right) \\ & + 12n(3n - 2) \times \left(\frac{1}{15} + \frac{1}{26}\right) + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{19}\right) + 12n \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{26}\right) \\ & + 6n(6n - 5) \times \left(\frac{1}{26} + \frac{1}{26}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3D plot of the third reverse R index of ZHK(n,p) network, , is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 3D plot of the third reverse R index of ZHK(n,p)

3.2 Entropies of ZHK(n,p)

The following theorems give the overall entropies which are based on Van, R, and S indices representation of ZHK(n,p).

Theorem 13. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second Van index of is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ent_{Van^2}(G) = & \log\left(\frac{273}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{144}n^2 - \frac{91}{16}np + \frac{9419}{432}n\right) \\
 & - \frac{1}{\frac{273}{16}n^2p - \frac{4811}{144}n^2 - \frac{91}{16}np + \frac{9419}{432}n} \left(6n \times \frac{25}{36} \times \log \frac{25}{36} + 12n \times \frac{35}{72} \times \log \frac{35}{72}\right. \\
 & \left. + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{7}{18} \times \log \frac{7}{18}\right. \\
 & \left. + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{8}{27} \times \log \frac{8}{27} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{49}{144} \times \log \frac{49}{144} + 12n \times \frac{7}{27} \times \log \frac{7}{27}\right. \\
 & \left. + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{16}{81} \times \log \frac{16}{81}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^2}(G) = \log(Van^2(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 1, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 14. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse Van index of is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = & \log\left(\frac{5832}{49}n^2p - \frac{10449}{196}n^2 - \frac{1944}{49}np - \frac{33183}{9800}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{5832}{49}n^2p - \frac{10449}{196}n^2 - \frac{1944}{49}np - \frac{33183}{9800}n} \left(6n \times \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{36}{25} \times \log \frac{36}{25} + 12n \times \frac{72}{35} \times \log \frac{72}{35} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{18}{7} \times \log \frac{18}{7}\right. \\
 & \left. + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{27}{8} \times \log \frac{27}{8} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{144}{49} \times \log \frac{144}{49} + 12n \times \frac{27}{7} \times \log \frac{27}{7}\right. \\
 & \left. + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{81}{16} \times \log \frac{81}{16}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = \log(Van^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 2, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 15. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^3}(G) = \log\left(\frac{111}{2}n^2p - \frac{189}{2}n^2 - \frac{37}{2}np - \frac{113}{2}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{111}{2}n^2p - \frac{189}{2}n^2 - \frac{37}{2}np - \frac{113}{2}n} \left(6n \times \frac{5}{3} \times \log \frac{5}{3} + 12n \times \frac{17}{12} \times \log \frac{17}{12} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{5}{4} \times \log \frac{5}{4} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{10}{9} \times \log \frac{10}{9} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{7}{6} \times \log \frac{7}{6} + 12n \times \frac{37}{36} \times \log \frac{37}{36} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{8}{9} \times \log \frac{8}{9}\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^3}(G) = \log(Van^3(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 3, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 16. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{1026}{7}n^2p - \frac{999}{7}n^2 - \frac{342}{7}np + \frac{1998}{35}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{1026}{7}n^2p - \frac{999}{7}n^2 - \frac{342}{7}np + \frac{1998}{35}n} \left(6n \times \frac{12}{5} \times \log \frac{12}{5} + 12n \times \frac{102}{35} \times \log \frac{102}{35} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{45}{14} \times \log \frac{45}{14} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{15}{4} \times \log \frac{15}{4} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{24}{7} \times \log \frac{24}{7} + 12n \times \frac{111}{28} \times \log \frac{111}{28} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{9}{2} \times \log \frac{9}{2}\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log(Van^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 4, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 17. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log(765n^2p + 2385n^2 - 255np - 2109n) - \frac{1}{765n^2p + 2385n^2 - 255np - 2109n} \left(12n \times 5 \times \log 5 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 15 \times \log 15 + 12n(3n - 2) \times 30 \times \log 30 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 25 \times \log 5 + 12n \times 50 \times \log 50 + 6n(6n - 5) \times 100 \times \log 100\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log(S^2(G)) - \frac{1}{S^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 5, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 18. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{7}{4}n^2p - \frac{2001}{484}n^2 - \frac{7}{12}np + \frac{2003}{484}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{7}{4}n^2p - \frac{2001}{484}n^2 - \frac{7}{12}np + \frac{2003}{484}n} \left(6n \times \frac{1}{4} \times \log \frac{1}{4} + 12n \times \frac{1}{12} \times \log \frac{1}{12} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{1}{24} \times \log \frac{1}{24} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{1}{44} \times \log \frac{1}{44} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{1}{36} \times \log \frac{1}{36} + 12n \times \frac{1}{66} \times \log \frac{1}{66} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{1}{121} \times \log \frac{1}{121}\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log(S^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 6, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 19. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(378n^2p + 54n^2 - 126np - 174n) - \frac{1}{378n^2p + 54n^2 - 126np - 174n} \left(6n \times 2 \times \log 2 + 12n \times 6 \times \log 6 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 8 \times \log 8 + 12n(3n - 2) \times 13 \times \log 13 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 10 \times \log 10 + 12n \times 15 \times \log 15 + 6n(6n - 5) \times 20 \times \log 20\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(S^3(G)) - \frac{1}{S^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 7, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 20. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(18n^2p - \frac{387}{11}n^2 - 6np + \frac{291}{11}n\right) - \frac{1}{18n^2p - \frac{387}{11}n^2 - 6np + \frac{291}{11}n} \left(12n \times \frac{2}{3} \times \log \frac{2}{3} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{5}{12} \times \log \frac{5}{12} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{15}{44} \times \log \frac{15}{44} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} + 12n \times \frac{17}{66} \times \log \frac{17}{66} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11}\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^3r}(G) = \log(S^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 8, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 21. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. Then, entropy of G which is based on the second R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^2}(G) = \log(13509n^2p - 2151n^2 - 4503np - 3549n) - \frac{1}{13509n^2p - 2151n^2 - 4503np - 3549n} (6n \times 121 \times \log 121 + 12n \times 209 \times \log 209 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 285 \times \log 285 + 12n(3n - 2) \times 390 \times \log 390 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 361 \times \log 361 + 12n \times 494 \times \log 494 + 6n(6n - 5) \times 676 \times \log 676)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^2}(G) = \log(R^2(G)) - \frac{1}{R^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 9, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 22. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{273}{1805}n^2p - \frac{94008}{305045}n^2 - \frac{91}{1805}np + \frac{16146783}{73820890}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{273}{1805}n^2p - \frac{94008}{305045}n^2 - \frac{91}{1805}np + \frac{16146783}{73820890}n} (6n \times \frac{1}{121} \times \log \frac{1}{121} + 12n \times \frac{1}{209} \times \log \frac{1}{209} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{1}{285} \times \log \frac{1}{285} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{1}{390} \times \log \frac{1}{390} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{1}{361} \times \log \frac{1}{361} + 12n \times \frac{1}{494} \times \log \frac{1}{494} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{1}{676} \times \log \frac{1}{676})$$

Proof. Considering that G is a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) = \log(R^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 10, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 23. Let G be a $ZHK(n,p)$ network. Then, entropy of G which is based on the third R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^3}(G) = \log(1566n^2p - 1350n^2 - 522np + 462n) - \frac{1}{1566n^2p - 1350n^2 - 522np + 462n} (6n \times 22 \times \log 22 + 12n \times 30 \times \log 30 + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times 34 \times \log 34 + 12n(3n - 2) \times 41 \times \log 41 + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times 38 \times \log 38 + 12n \times 45 \times \log 45 + 6n(6n - 5) \times 52 \times \log 52$$

)

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^3}(G) = \log(R^3(G)) - \frac{1}{R^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 11, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 24. Let G be a ZHK(n,p) network. Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{498}{95}n^2p - \frac{11328}{1235}n^2 - \frac{166}{95}np + \frac{78106}{13585}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{498}{95}n^2p - \frac{11328}{1235}n^2 - \frac{166}{95}np + \frac{78106}{13585}n} \left(6n \times \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11} + 12n \times \frac{30}{209} \times \log \frac{30}{209} + 12n(3np - p - 9n + 4) \times \frac{34}{285} \times \log \frac{34}{285} + 12n(3n - 2) \times \frac{41}{390} \times \log \frac{41}{390} + 3n(p - 3)(3n - 1) \times \frac{2}{19} \times \log \frac{2}{19} + 12n \times \frac{45}{494} \times \log \frac{45}{494} + 6n(6n - 5) \times \frac{1}{13} \times \log \frac{1}{13}\right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a ZHK(n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^{3r}}(G) = \log(R^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 12, the conclusion follows.

4. Conclusions

The generalized mathematical expression for R , S , and Van topological indices for structures of ZHK(n,p) is described in this study. Information-theoretic entropy measurements of various phases of 2D materials of ZHK(n,p)s are provided by these generalized mathematical formulations. The structures examined here were shown to have very little variation in their entropies. These many phases of ZHK(n,p) might be predicted in terms of their thermochemistry, physicochemical properties, electrical, optical, and mechanical characteristics using our proposed topological indices and entropy metrics. Additionally, these indices can be combined with metrics derived from quantum chemistry, such as molecular hardness, polarizability measures, atomic charges, etc., to create a platform that is robust in predicting molecular connectivity and electronic-based attributes. Numerous probabilistic entropy metrics are produced using the same indices that Shannon's formula uses to define the probability function. We create a connection between the degree-based entropies of and structures using their respective degree-based topological indices. By linking the architectures of and ZHK(n,p) with a number of their physicochemical and optoelectronic properties, the results of this study could significantly advance QSAR and QSPR studies of these materials.

Dedication: This article is dedicated to all our Palestinian Muslim brothers and sisters who were martyred in the attacks of the cruel terrorist state of Israel. Long live free and prosperous PALESTINE.

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